

Formation of aggregated neutrophil extracellular traps in tissues is determining the efficacy of particulate nanoadjuvants

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Abstract

Neutrophils are essential for innate immunity, using mechanisms like Neutrophil Extracellular Trap (NET) formation to fight pathogens. Aggregated NETs (aggNETs) help resolve inflammation by cleaving pro-inflammatory cytokines, while scattered NETs can exacerbate inflammation, leading to tissue damage. Co-injection of 10 nm nanodiamonds (ND10) with peptide antigens boosts immune responses, including anti-SARS-CoV-2 immunity, due to transient immune responses induced by aggNETs around ND10 particles. Diamond nanoparticles in adjuvant mixtures enhance vaccines, though the optimal dose is uncertain. Our study aimed to find the minimal ND10 amount needed for effective aggNETs formation and a robust immune response with minimal long-term tissue damage. In vivo experiments revealed 1mg of ND10 per injection significantly enhances immune responses,

forming granulomas rich in neutrophil elastase. Lower doses left scattered nanoparticles, insufficient for aggNETs formation. The effective ND10 dose for mice, 1 mg per injection, can be extrapolated to other organisms.

Keywords: neutrophils, neutrophil extracellular traps (NETs), adjuvants, inflammation, immunization

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Introduction

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3 Neutrophils are pivotal players in innate immunity, wielding an array of mechanisms like
4 phagocytosis, degranulation, and the recently uncovered process of NETosis (Neutrophil
5 Extracellular Trap formation) [1]. These cells detect particulate invaders through pattern recognition
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7 receptors (PRRs), aided by opsonizing proteins like antibodies or complement [2]. This innate
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9 response aims to eliminate foreign particles effectively. NETosis serves as a final defense
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11 mechanism employed by neutrophils when other methods of combating foreign invaders prove
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13 ineffective. Diamond nanoparticles, known for their stability, resistance to oxidation, and protease
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15 resistance, exhibit a super hydrophobic surface and serve as a good example of such particulate
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17 invaders when injected into the body. Specifically, nanodiamonds around 10nm in size (referred to
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19 as ND10) act as potent inducers of NETs, prompting extensive NETs formation and their
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21 aggregations with the aim of entrapping and passivation [3].
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28 Aggregated NETs, termed aggNETs, have emerged as key regulators of inflammation resolution.
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30 These structures, rich in neutrophil proteases, facilitate inflammation damping by cleaving pro-
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32 inflammatory cytokines [4]. Notably, aggNETs formation is ROS-dependent and occurs when a
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34 significant stimulus accumulates in one location [5]. However, scattered NETs can exacerbate
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36 inflammation, contributing to autoimmune diseases and tissue damage [6]. Their unchecked
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38 production may lead to various complications, including thrombosis and lung pathologies [7].
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43 Artificial induction of aggregated NETs in tissues involves injecting high concentrations of inert
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45 particles. Neutrophils employ NETosis to passivate non-destructible objects, revealing a universal
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47 response to inert nanoparticles [8]. This causes massive neutrophil infiltration, followed by other
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49 immune cells, formation of NETs, aggregating ND10 and NETs and forming aggNETs around
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51 particles, followed by the cytokine degradation by aggNETs and ensuring self-limited, transient
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53 immune response. Interestingly, protein or peptide antigens co-injected with inert nanoparticles
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55 trigger the induction of immune responses against them [3], thus nanoparticles acting as a vaccine
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57 adjuvant. This phenomenon led to the concept of using nanoparticle-induced NETs to stimulate an
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59 immune response against co-injected antigens, and was so far utilized for enhancing adjuvant
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61 properties of aluminum nanowires [9], nanodiamonds with covalently linked pan-coronaviral peptides
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[10], nanodiamonds with adsorbed protein corona of SARS-CoV-2 recombinant peptides [11], enhancing the adjuvant action of oil emulsions [12], and others. Recent findings suggest NETs involvement in most types of vaccines including alum, reviewed in [13].

While utilizing ND10 mixture with protein antigens, we aimed to determine the minimum amount or concentration(s) of ND10 still triggering NETs formation and subsequent pronounced immune response to antigens while providing minimal negative influence on the contacting tissues. These questions were addressed in current study.

Results and Discussion

Determining effective nanoadjuvant concentration for blood cells ex vivo

The DCFH-DA dye was added to freshly heparinized blood, which was then treated with ND10 at varying concentrations. Needle-shaped crystals of monosodium urate (MSU) were used as a positive control for NETs induction, as described in [14]. The treated blood samples (cells + ND10) were co-incubated, after which red blood cells were lysed, and flow cytometry was performed with gating on polymorphonuclear neutrophils (PMNs) to measure ROS levels associated with NET production.

A significant increase in reactive oxygen species (ROS) was observed within 2 hours of co-incubation with ND10, peaking sharply before gradually declining by the 6-hour mark. In contrast, MSU-triggered activation had a slower onset, peaking at 6 hours (Figure 1). Based on these observations and the kinetics of MSU-induced NET formation as referenced in [15,16], we extrapolated the appropriate ND10 concentrations for in vivo testing.

Immune-inducing potency of different amounts of nanoadjuvants

Immunization of 5 groups of mice was done using Freund's adjuvants (CFA/IFA) as positive controls [17,18], and employing 3 doses of ND10 - 1 mg, 0.5 mg, and 0.2 mg per injection, corresponding to doses of 40, 20 and 8 mg/kg of body weight, and antigen used w/o adjuvant as control group (denoted as 0). In all cases ovalbumin served as the antigen (100 µg, per

immunization), which was also used to determine the level of generated antibodies and to induce the delayed-type hypersensitivity (DTH) reaction. Following a standard immunization protocol, animals received two injections (Figure. 2C) on days 1 and 15. On day 28, we induced the cellular immune response reaction (DTH) and assessed the response's relative strength (Figure 2B). The cellular response was notably lower for the 0.5 mg ($p=0.053$) and 0.2 mg doses per injection ($p<0.01$) compared to the 1 mg/injection dose. Blood samples were collected on day 35, with sera isolated for anti-OVA IgG detection (Figure. 2A). The 1 mg ND10 dose proved significantly more potent in both humoral and cellular immune responses. Antibody levels were monitored over the immunization period, with a significant increase in IgG only observed on day 35. Data for the 0.2 and 1 mg ND10 doses are presented in Figure. 2C.

Aggregation of nanoadjuvants in tissues

We selected doses of 0.2 mg ND10 and 1 mg ND10 per injection coated with protein antigen according to the described method [11], for intramuscular (i.m.) and subcutaneous (s.c.) administration in mice with subsequent histological analysis of injection sites after 30 days. We observed the formation of clearly defined granulomas surrounded by connective tissue for the 1 mg dose, whereas remnants of ND10 were scattered in tissues for the 0.2 mg dose, indicating insufficient nanoparticles to form aggregated NETs around them (Figure 3).

Long-term nanoparticle encapsulation in granulomas

To study the long-term effects of ND10 injections, we analyzed subcutaneous granulomas at the injection site of ND10 particles coated with a protein antigen, isolated 9 months after the initial immunization. Parallel tissue sections, 5 μm thick, were stained with H&E and subjected to immunohistochemistry (IHC) to detect neutrophil elastase (NE) and DNA. Given NE's high stability—evident even in gallstones after prolonged storage [8]—it was selected as a potential marker for detecting NETs months after formation.

As shown in Figure 4, the large ND10 deposits (Figures 4A and 4B, appearing black due to high light absorption by ND10) were enveloped by tissue. These deposits also tested positive for NE

(Figure 4C), with numerous cell nuclei (Figure 4D) dispersed between the areas of nanoparticle deposition. In contrast, some small ND10 deposits (Figures 4B&C, highlighted in red) were NE-negative.

Aggregated nanoadjuvants are infiltrated with immune cells

The significant presence of cell nuclei surrounding ND10 deposits led us to perform further high-magnification analysis, revealing ND10 deposits within multinucleated giant cells—a specialized subset of macrophages involved in handling foreign bodies and recently associated with immune modulation [19] (Figure 4F-H, indicated with *). These multinucleated macrophages were surrounded by numerous leukocytes (Figure 4F-G, indicated with arrows), suggesting an active immune-modulating role, and by fibroblast-like cells forming a connective tissue capsule around the injected ND10 particles. All observed cells at the ND10 injection site were viable, with no signs of inflammation or necrosis.

The presence of ND10 deposits within aggNETs (as indicated by neutrophil elastase [NE] staining in green, Figure 4H) and subsequent phagocytosis by macrophages support the involvement of aggNETs in the ND10-induced immune response. Additionally, the high density of lymphoid cells at the injection site likely enhances the immunogenic potency of the nanoadjuvants used.

The data suggest that achieving a specific concentration of ND10 in tissues triggers NET formation, which then aggregates into aggNETs. This finding supports the hypothesis that inducing a potent immune response depends not on dose-dependence but on reaching a critical mass of nanoadjuvants to drive aggNET formation. The minimum effective dose was determined to be 1 mg per injection. Given the size similarity between human and mouse neutrophils, this dose can be feasibly applied for human injections.

Materials and Methods

Materials. Nanodiamonds were obtained from Merck (Diamond nanopowder, < 10 nm particle size, Nr. 636428, D10). Recombinant part of S-protein of SARS-CoV-2 with the sequence NITNLCPFGEVFNATRFASVYAWNRKRISNVCVADYSVLYNSASFSTFKCYGVSPSTKLNLDLCFTNVY

ADSFVIRGDEVQRQIAPGQTGKIADYNYKLPDDFTGCVIAWNSNNLDSKVGGNYNLYRLFRKSNLK
PFERDISTEIQAGSTPCNGVEGFNCYFPLQSYGFQPTNGVGYQPVRVVLSFELLHAPATV with
99% purity was obtained from Explogen, Ukraine. The protein was expressed in E.coli, the culture
was lysed and hydrophobic protein was dissolved in buffer containing 6M guanidine chloride, 400
mM NaCl and 20 mM Tris-HCl (solubilizing buffer, SB) and was shown to elicit strong immunogenic
effect [20]. Hydrophilic part of peptide with the sequence of
DDFTGCVIAWNSNNLDSKVGGNYNLYRLFRKSNLKPFERDISTEIQAG was obtained from
ProteoGenix, France and was used for DTH test.

Whole blood ROS detection. Heparinized blood samples were incubated with 5 μ M
dichlorodihydrofluorescein diacetate (DCFH-DA) for 30 minutes at 37°C and 5% CO₂. Then, blood
was lysed and cells were analyzed in Dx-FLEX flow cytometer, Beckman Coulter. Excitation of
fluorescence was at 488 nm, and emission at 525 \pm 40 nm gating on granulocyte population.
Fluorescence data were analyzed using CytExpert software.

Animals. Studies involving animals, including housing and care, method of euthanasia, and
experimental protocols were approved by the Ethical committee of Danylo Halytsky Lviv National
Medical University, protocols 20191216/10, 20210622/6, all experiments were designed to comply
with principles of the 3Rs (Replacement, Reduction and Refinement). Balb/c mice were housed in a
temperature/humidity/light controlled environment, with both food and drinking water available *ad
libitum*. Animals weighting at least 23-25 g were used for immunization experiments.

Animal immunization. Mice immunization was done using balb/c mice as described previously [9].
Mixture of ND covered with pancoronaviral protein or ovalbumin (OVA) were used for immunization.
The **DTH test** [21] was performed 28 days after the 1st immunization by injection of 5 μ g of protein
in PBS (50 μ l) in into the right hind paw. **ELISA tests** for testing the level of specific anti-OVA
antibodies we used a standard approach described in in our previous reports [10,22].

Histological analysis including tissue fixation, histological preparations, hematoxylin eosin staining
(H&E) were made according to standard established procedures. Fluorescent staining of
deparafinized tissue sections were performed with a proprietary probe for neutrophil elastase (NE)
(Lectinotest R&D, UA and Kyushu Institute of Technology, JP, patent pending). The probe consist

of a peptide mimicking the binding site of a natural inhibitor of NE conjugated with infrared fluorescent SQ dye [23].

Fluorescent microscopy. Fluorescent microscopy was performed with an Keyence BZ-X800 fluorescent microscope (Keyence, Japan) using both 40x 0.95NA and 100x 1.45NA oil immersion objectives. All image analysis was performed under a fixed setting of parameters including exposure and compensation.

Data analysis. The mean values were used to construct data on the figures. For comparisons between two groups, the Mann–Whitney U-test for numerical variables was used. All analyses were performed using LibreOffice Calc (LibreOffice Community) and Prism 8.2 (GraphPad, San Diego, USA) software. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Four levels of significance are depicted in the figures by asterisks: * – $p < 0.05$; ** – $p < 0.01$; *** – $p < 0.001$.

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Figure legends

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Figure 1. Activation of human blood cells ex vivo under the influence of ND10 and MSU. All green and red dots significantly differ from control values.

Figure 2. Immune response to different doses of ND10 adjuvant. A – Humoral immune response, detected as levels of anti-OVA IgG in serum by ELISA. B – Cellular immune response detected as footpad swelling at DTH reaction. C – dynamics of IgG changes during the course of immunization for selected ND10 concentrations (0,2 and 1 mg per doze).

Figure 3. Histological analysis of intramuscular and subcutaneous injections of nanodiamonds at the specified doses. Nanodiamond particles are indicated by arrows.

Figure 4. Areas of localized ND10 particles isolated from animal 9-month post immunization. A – overview of tissues analyzed, H&E staining, B – D – parallel section of A, corresponding to area within white square. B – BF microscopy, demonstrating light-absorbing ND10 particles, C – NE (visualized green), D – DNA (red) and E – overlay of C and D. Red squared indicate areas of scattered ND10 particles negative for NE signal. High magnification (F-H) of areas rich in ND10 reveal their presence in multinucleated giant cells (*),surrounded by leukocytes (yellow arrows) many of them expressing NE (visualized green at F). The insert represent H&E staining.

Figure 1

Figure2

Figure3

Figure4

